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Assessment of Taekwondo Training Program: Basis for Innovative Training Design

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Abstract

This study focused on the assessment of the Taekwondo training program in the division Alaminos City for the School Year 2022-2023. It used a descriptive research design. The total respondents consist of ninety-six (96) taekwondo athletes from Public and Private Secondary Schools in the School Division of Alaminos City with four years-experience as a taekwondo athlete. The study found out that in the status of taekwondo training program, the athletes are moderately satisfied with their training on basic movements (kibondongjak), and sparring (kyorugi); and very satisfied with their training on form (poomsae). For the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program, the athletes found the training on physical fitness, mental health, and emotional development to be effective. In the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program, the athletes are very highly satisfied with their pre-training and training proper; while they are very highly satisfied with their post training. And, with the challenges encountered by the athletes in the taekwondo training program, the athletes have a high encounter. The study recommends that in the status of taekwondo training program, there should be a review and revision to be made to suit the training needs of the athletes particularly on basic movements (kibondongjak), and sparring (kyorugi) since they found it moderately satisfying. Likewise, in the implementation of taekwondo training program, the sports officials, coaches and trainers should focus more on the training of athletes particularly on physical fitness, mental health, and emotional development. Also, in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program, sports officials, coaches and trainers should strengthen the pre-training and proper training activities of the athletes. Further, on the challenges encountered by the athletes, the SDO personnel concern, coaches and trainers should always attend to the needs of the athletes to enhance their performance and be always on guard of their welfare. Finally, an innovative training design is being proposed.

Keywords: *taekwondo, assessment, training program, athlete*

Introduction

Globally, the success of a training program is based on the performance of the athletes. An effective training program is key to winning, for its goal is to improve the skills or talents of the athletes. As stated by the Sports Industry Research Center (2003) One of the sports applying to the said programs is Taekwondo. Taekwondo (TKD) is part of acyclic sports and is a heuristic sport as the adversarial relationship involves solving the opposition through motor actions, often original, depending on various conditions.

With the continuous development of education reform, the education department is gradually committed to the comprehensive cultivation of athletes' moral, intellectual, physical, aesthetic, and labor. As one of the physical education courses, Taekwondo has gradually been valued and introduced by some schools. However, although some schools have introduced Taekwondo courses, there are some problems with few courses, insufficient equipment, and low student 'interest, which bring adverse effects on the promotion of Taekwondo and the cultivation of students' physical quality.

Training is the process whereby technical skills are enhanced. Planned strength training aims to increase basic physical power. Physical strength means the functional capability of the body. Such ability is the basis of physical activity. However, the notion that one's physical strength may be enhanced without any relation to sports techniques implies a goal for the enhancement of the harmonious progress of both physical strength and athletic ability. When each one of these factors in training is equally developed in two competitors, the winner and the loser are determined by the psychological edge. Physical preparation is one of the most important factors, which must be considered for the enhancement of competitive ability at higher levels (Asian Taekwondo Union 2019).

As stated in Asian Taekwondo Union (2019), changes in the human body's structure and function occur slowly, over a long period. Deliberate planning is needed for the functional improvement of the nervous system to take place. Therefore, training methods to develop sports techniques must follow basic principles. That is, one must proceed from simple movements step by step, to effectively guide the development of the body's abilities. It is important to train consistently. For example, there is no gain in continuously training for six months and then resting for six months. Consistent regular training, and one must aim for the most desirable quality and quantity of training. The proper amount of high-caliber regular training done consistently is essential for success.

One of the factors that need to assess in such a training program is the status of the athlete, according to the development of its components, the more the elements are higher, the more the athlete's level was raised. It is worth mentioning that there should be consistency between the development degree of these components, according to the requirements of competitive performance, to allow the athlete to reach the formation of the sports (Tønnessen et.al, 2011).

Assessment in a Taekwondo training program is necessary to assess the achievement of its current and operational nature as well as to highlight any functional, morphological, motor, and mental products for the improvement and adaptation condition to high-intensity

efforts, volume, and complexity. The main objective of the assessment is a prerequisite for conducting scientific sports. In the study of Kim et al. (2021) on the psychosocial effects of taekwondo trainings, findings show that a meta-analysis of these supports that taekwondo can have a positive impact on the psychosocial factors of trainees.

The physical preparation among Taekwondo athletes is considered the support's core in the annual training plan, during its period and at different stages. The importance of the physical aspect was assured scientifically and technically, in addition to being related to the technical aspect. Therefore, the physical aspect can't be separated from the technical one at any preparation stages, also during the competition. Physical training aims at achieving a high level of performance, by raising the Taekwondo athletes' training level, combining physical skills, planning and knowledge, and psychological elements. The training case is a term that expresses the athlete's abilities and the readiness of the body organs during training and competitions. According to Fong (2011), Taekwondo training has a positive impact on physical health, such as improving physical fitness and body composition, and also on psychological, social, and cognitive health.

In addition, many individuals from approximately 209 countries are conducting Taekwondo training. According to World Taekwondo (2017), Taekwondo training is performed in Taekwondo gymnasiums in each country. Therefore, the training program in Taekwondo gymnasiums has a significant factor on the effect of Taekwondo training. However, the effects of Taekwondo training on the same physical fitness factors greatly varied among studies. The study of Ouerghi et al. (2020) on the repeated sprint training vs repeated high intensity technique training in adolescent taekwondo athletes, found out that the number of techniques during the 1-minute specific exercise was higher in repeated sprint training and repeated training technique compared to the control group for the dominant leg. Delta lactate at post training was lower for repeated training technique for both legs compared to repeated sprint training and control group.

Coyne et al. (2018) claimed that it is often thought that physical training is essential in Taekwondo sports. To effectively understand the full extent of the demands of a sport, researchers must not only examine the demands and implications of the competition itself but also the methods that coaches and athletes employ to prepare for competition. In open-skill sports such as Taekwondo, where athletes are required to react to unpredictable and changing externally paced environments.

Furthermore, Wasll (2018) explains that Taekwondo training can increase strength and muscle tone, reduce body fat, improve cardiovascular conditioning and endurance, improve balance and coordination, reduce stress, improve concentration and focus, improve performance in one's job, school, or sports, provide a structured program of advancement with achievable goals, and improve self-discipline and self-confidence.

As stated in RA 053, s. 2022, WT is included in the 28 sports which are governed by the International Federation. Many refresher courses were issued by the DepEd to ensure the implementation of Taekwondo in the country is smooth and properly implemented. Among these issuances includes Division Memorandum 797,2022 of the Schools Division of Davao Del Norte. The Division Memorandum 556s s. 2017 of the Schools Division of Bohol.

Taekwondo, as one of the sports competitive activities, has gradually attracted the attention of some middle schools and has been introduced into the physical education classroom to enrich the content of physical education teaching and to improve students' physical literacy (Wang 2021).

Taekwondo associations both in the public and private sectors are generally faced with the problem of insufficient professional quality of Taekwondo training programs and single curriculum content, which harms the improvement of Taekwondo athletes' actual ability, based on the development of Taekwondo courses. In this regard, it is necessary to actively improve the quality of training programs, innovate the types of Taekwondo courses, and stimulate athletes' interests in various forms such as competitive activities and competitions, to improve athletes' Taekwondo literacy (Liang 2019).

Zhang Peng (2018) explored the impact of practical teaching on athletes' Taekwondo quality in research and found that the shortage of equipment and lack of practical training are important factors affecting athletes' enthusiasm and Taekwondo quality. In this regard, we need to actively introduce Taekwondo equipment to meet the needs of athletes, and actively innovate the Taekwondo practice training mode, to further improve the level of students' Taekwondo.

Taekwondo sports have developed into an increasingly popular combat sport. As proof, in the year 2000, Taekwondo was already introduced to the Olympic Games making the professionalism and competitiveness of the sport at a higher level and become dramatically increasing. Taekwondo needs to attain its aims, and one of the aims of Taekwondo is to achieve a technical knockout or to score more points than the opponent through kicks and punches to the body and kicks to the head.

Taekwondo course in junior high school has a high degree of discipline, which is conducive to improving the athletes' comprehensive quality and Taekwondo etiquette, thus improving the comprehensive quality of junior high school athletes at a certain level. However, in actual training, coaches, and trainers only pay attention to the training of basic moves, and the training of physical fitness and etiquette is a mere formality, which cannot meet the overall educational needs. For this, it is necessary to actively consolidate the physical fitness training of athletes and strengthen the etiquette training of athletes, which can better improve the comprehensive quality of Taekwondo athletes (Liu, 2022).

Consequently, as stated in Paragraph 37, UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Taekwondo is an essential sport that gained lots of global achievements for is also an important enabler of sustainable development. It was emphasized that the growing contribution of sport to the realization of development and peace in its promotion of tolerance and respect and the contributions it makes to the empowerment of women and young people, individuals, and communities as well as to health, education, and social inclusion objectives

Moreover, Taekwondo sports has become a popular sport not only in other countries but as well as in the Philippines. In the Philippines, many federations of Taekwondo have existed. Taekwondo is considered a combat sport that is contested between two fighters in a ring that measures 8m in diameter. The object of the game is to win a contest by either point or by knockout (Studuco, 2021).

Furthermore, Taekwondo is also an internationally established martial art, included in the Olympic Games, and is practiced today by millions of people in more than 200 countries (International Olympic Committee, 2021). Despite some controversies regarding its origin and history, Taekwondo is known to have evolved from a form of unarmed military training of ancient kingdoms of the Korean peninsula. Taekwondo training in the US was for utilized health and physical-strength improvements in the past; however, approaches that address the value of education has recently become more popular. About prior studies, Taekwondo training during the elementary school period has positive effects on physical, cognitive, emotional, and social development (Chang & Hwang, 2017).

Taekwondo is a martial art form that originated in Korea and has been adopted as an official Olympic sport since the Sydney Olympics in 2000. It is a popular sport worldwide, with about 80 million individuals from more than 200 countries participating (Kazemi et al., 2006; Lee & Kim, 2015). The number of children and adults participating in martial arts, including taekwondo, has been increasing by 20%–25% annually, and taekwondo is a popular sport among children (Lee & Kim, 2015).

Taekwondo has played a key role in the improvement of a humanist education that values courtesy and respect, as well as in the prevention of a diversity of crimes by contributing to the physical training and values education of American students. In addition, taekwondo has been recognized as one of the most effective methods to cultivate desirable values and attitudes in adolescents through the internalization of social norms, beliefs, values, attitudes, and cognitive experiences (Lim & Kim, 2011).

In general, physical activities affect human social life in various ways, and inherent values directly impact psychological reactions and achievement behaviors (Schwartz, 1992). As the value of participating in physical activities through sports helps the individual's psychological adaptation and improves social support, we can see that it plays a critical role in healthy adaptation to school life. In this respect, physical activity through taekwondo training is considered very important for school education within the US.

Taekwondo training in the US was focused on health and physical-strength improvements in the past; however, approaches that address the value of education have recently become more popular. About prior studies, taekwondo training during the elementary school period has positive effects on physical, cognitive, emotional, and social development (Chang & Hwang, 2017; Lee & Song, 2006). Taekwondo has positive influences on trainees' psychological constructs such as willpower (Kim, 2005), concentration (Kim & Kim, 2000), and self-regulation (Lakes & Hoyt, 2004). Also, taekwondo trainees have a lower acculturative stress level than non-trainees, and cope effectively with it (Kim et al., 2012). Another study on taekwondo elementary school trainees in the US pointed out that taekwondo positively developed sociability and mental health (Lee, 2010). Lakes (2013) stated that the expectation regarding taekwondo training comprises the improvement of exercise capabilities and psychological benefits.

In addition, Lakes et al. (2013) reported that taekwondo training positively affected the self-control, execution functions, class behaviors, and exercise functions of young student subjects. The training also affected the school adaptation of the young students, as they experienced corresponding favorable effects regarding their relationships with teachers, their relationships with friends, and school classes and norms.

According to Kukkiwon (2015), Taekwondo training has long been reported to be effective in enhancing the social traits of practitioners, Sociality, is a distinctly human trait that prompts the need to associate with social groups is a fundamental characteristic of survival and coexistence with others. According to a study that investigated the correlation between self-regulation and sociality in elementary school students practicing Taekwondo, depending on the duration, the training period explained differences in diligence, interpersonal relationships, and responsibility, suggesting that regular Taekwondo training has a positive effect on social development and adaptation to the group.

From an analysis of the impact of the exercise values in the US. Taekwondo trainees on school-life adaptation, the subfactors of exercise values (general, moral, and status) partly affected the subfactors of school-life adaptation (school activities, teachers, rules, and academic activities). More specifically, the general and moral values affected all of the subfactors, while the status values affected both rule adaptation and adaptation to academic activities.

Similar results were reported by previous studies. A study on the value of taekwondo training reported that the child participants of taekwondo training in the study thought more highly of moral and rule compliance than the child participants of other sports, thereby providing support for the results of this study. Previous studies also show the existence of positive effects regarding the cultivation of ethical attitudes that is achieved through the nurturing of the spirits of the taekwondo trainees (Lakes & Hoyt, 2004; Lakes et al., 2013)

In addition, some existing studies report similar results regarding the positive impact of exercise values on school-life adaptation. Following an analysis of the school-life-adaptation difference between taekwondo participants and nonparticipants. Also, Lim and Kim

(2011) reported that sports activities favorably affect school-life adaptation. Therefore, it is demonstrated that long participation in taekwondo would have a positive effect on pro-social behaviors (Koo & Lee, 2014).

Previous studies by Lim and Kim (2011) indicate that taekwondo training can contribute to learning and academic activity improvements, inspire the sociability that is necessary for school life, and promote cooperation, unity, and school affection that are necessary for organizational life. Additionally, it is expected that healthy physical activities like taekwondo will not only mean that adolescents are steered in a beneficial direction during troubled and stressful times, but that school-life adaptation is facilitated by inspiration of confidence, cooperation, a spirit of service, and sociability; furthermore, the adolescents will be enabled to engage in experiences such as pleasure, emotional purification, and a sense of accomplishment through their voluntary participation.

Most developing nations rely on government funding to sustain their sports program, the Philippines notwithstanding. Elite sport development in the country is dependent on harmonious coordination between the Philippine Sports Commission (PSC) and the Philippine Olympic Committee (POC). The PSC was created through Republic Act No. 6847 to serve as the "sole policy-making and coordinating body of all amateur sports development programs and institutions in the Philippines." While the POC is a private, non-profit organization recognized by the International Olympic Committee (IOC) as having the sole authority for representation of the Philippines in the Olympic Games, Asian Games, Southeast Asian Games, and other multievent competitions.

Based on the study by Lim and Kim (2011), taekwondo helps the growth and development of children and youth, it has a greater utility in the cultivation of ideal human beings that is combined with a holistic, humanist education that fosters the formation of great personalities, and it improves physical strength through physical activities. These benefits are regarded as very favorable factors for the cultivation of the personalities of US students who can be exposed to potentially harmful social elements such as gun possession and drugs. Taekwondo training enables students to maintain a relationship with school rules, order, academic activities, and teachers; moreover, the training also helps students to form rational judgments regarding peer-related conflicts, and it, therefore, contributes to the educational value of public education.

Taekwondo is a high-intensity intermittent sport that, requires athletes to develop aerobic and anaerobic energy systems along with strength, power, speed, agility, and flexibility. It is also a highly technical and tactical sport that necessitates the proficient execution of complex skills such as kicking, punching, blocking, and footwork techniques. For taekwondo athletes to gain the technical and physical expertise required for success, they must partake in an adequate skill-based and physical preparation training program (Chen et al., 2017).

Investigations examining the routine training schedules of taekwondo athletes in the literature are relatively scarce. However, only one study reported the average session duration and frequency of specific taekwondo training of collegiate taekwondo athletes in the USA as being 2 ± 0.8 hours and 4 ± 1.2 days per week, respectively (Covarrubias et al., 2015)

Another study that tracked four athletes for 9 weeks in the lead-up to the 2008 Beijing Olympic Games reported their training program over this period as consisting of 3 strength sessions, 1 repeated-sprint conditioning session, 5 taekwondo skill-based sessions, and 3 passive recovery sessions (hydrotherapy and massage) per week (Ball, Nolan and Wheeler, 2011). They also reported that athletes participated in a periodized strength training program in which intensity was undulated between medium and high and was focused on strength and power.

Training, in the context of exercise and sports performance, is undertaken to physically and physiologically prepare athletes for the demands of the sport. To increase physical capacity, stress must first be applied to the body. Seminal work in the 50s was the first to describe the stress-recovery-adaptation curve. The detailed physiology of this is beyond the scope of this thesis but can be summarized as follows: the perturbation of homeostasis brought about by the stress of exercise moral and rule compliance than the child participants of other sports, thereby providing support for the results of this study. Previous studies also show the existence of positive effects regarding the cultivation of ethical attitudes that is achieved through the nurturing of the spirits of the taekwondo trainees (Lakes & Hoyt, 2004; Lakes et al., 2013).

Taekwondo can be largely divided into Kyorugi, Poomsae, and Breaking, etc. among them, Taekwondo Poomsae is a technical system based on the basic movements of attack and defense technology which assuming the situation of fighting and can be practiced alone [16–18]. At the same time, as a martial arts sport in which martial arts and sports spirit were determined together, it not only Meaning of the practice of Tao and courtesy but also emphasized spiritual cultivation.

Generally, Taekwondo Poomsae refers to Official Poomsae, and recently, to induce diversity and interest in Taekwondo training programs, Music Taekwondo or Taekwon Gymnastics, Rhythm Taekwondo, and Taekwondance, which are based on the basic movements of Taekwondo and recreated with music, are diversified and activated.

Also, Taekwondo training is effective in improving physical fitness, promoting exercise performance, resolving body imbalance, improving balance, improving body composition and blood composition, promoting physical development, and improving health status, etc. Interestingly, in most of these studies, the intervention means are Kyorugi rather than Poomsae.

This may be because Kyorugi is an official Olympic event, which is widely spread all over the world, with a high penetration rate and more practitioners. Despite this, we still found some research on the effects of Poomsae training. Seo and Park (2017) found that after

12 weeks of quality intervention, not only the physical condition of primary school students was improved, but also the dynamic and static balance was improved, and it was considered that the quality of Taekwondo was an effective sport. The study of Park and Seo (2017) showed that 12-week Taekwondo can improve the posture stability and sports performance of primary school students, and it is also very effective in reducing the physical imbalance and improving the physical function of the growing children, and the study by Jo (2006) & Lee (2010) said that after implementing a 12-week Poomsae training program, participants' blood TC, TG, LDL-C decreased, and HDL-C increased.

In addition, some researchers have Poomsae intervention studies on overweight or obese people and people with metabolic syndrome and the results of these studies showed that after 12 weeks of Poomsae intervention, participants' weight, BMI, and body fat rate decreased, and risk factors for obesity and metabolic syndromes such as waist circumference, blood glucose, triglycerides in the blood, and Cystatin C, etc. were significantly improved.

Based on this evidence, we have reason to believe that Taekwondo Poomsae is not only a very effective exercise method to help healthy or obese children improve their physique but also a very effective exercise method for the early prevention of lifestyle diseases and metabolic syndrome caused by obesity. However, some researchers reported that after Taekwondo Poomsae training, the improvement of body composition and physical fitness did not show statistical significance or the improvement effect is not ideal.

In this way, researchers made various attempts to verify the physical effects of the Poomsae training, but the results of the previous studies were diverse, and the effects were insignificant or statistically insignificant. Therefore, there is a limit to conclusively presenting appropriate information on improving body composition, blood components, and physical fitness.

Sport has proven to have vast applications in the promotion of health, education, nationalism, and developmental goals. It was in 1966 that the first formal sport management program was created to address the increasing complexities of managing sports, recreation, and athletic programs in various educational, public, and commercial settings (Zeigler, 2007). Sport is also one of the fastest-growing industries and impacts many aspects of the economy such as tourism, infrastructure, and entertainment (Gillentine & Crow, 2005).

To be well-versed in Taekwondo players one must master the skills. Basic movements (kibondongjak). Fundamentals of Taekwondo, constituting the bases of the whole series of taekwondo techniques. It is an intentional action to move the body as well as the hand and feet for offense and defense activities. To be proficient in taekwondo, it is important for one to first master the basic movements. Poomsae is a set of systematic series of movements, which incorporate the idea of attacking and defensive techniques against imaginary opponents. It can be considered as a form of choreography that captures the essence of Taekwondo. Poomsae practice helps in the development of rhythm, balance, coordination, endurance, patience, muscles, discipline, and proper breath control. It is also a convenient and effective form of taekwondo training for all ages, gender, and physical abilities. (Acme Taewondo 2021)

Stated also in Acme Taekwondo (2021) that two opponents exchange techniques with active movements and poses, that include a mirage of foot skills. It enables practitioners to build and maintain a strong body through vigorous muscle exercise and also develop confidence, courage, self-reliance, quick thinking, and respect for one's fellow men. The outstanding feature of sparring is the provision of a practical experience for practitioners to stand alone and face a series of difficult problems that call for split-second decisions. In Kyorugi competition, it is governed by a set of rules and regulations designed by the World Taekwondo. The aim is to eliminate injurious techniques. Similarly, the safety aspect is further enforced by the mandatory use of headgear, body protectors, hand gloves, groin guards, mouth guards, shin guards as well as forearm guards.

Taekwondo is considered suitable as an essential exercise for improving the physical activity of Koreans and preventing and improving various diseases. However, although multiple studies have been conducted to verify the effectiveness of Taekwondo training, the results are not consistent, and depend on the study subject, method, and duration of interventions, making it difficult to generalize the results. Therefore, it is necessary to present the best evidence to prove the effect of physical activity through Taekwondo among Koreans [Thus, this study shows the effects of Taekwondo training on changes in body composition comprehensively and quantitatively to serve as evidence for the development of Taekwondo training as a war to improve obesity caused by lack of exercise in modern people including not only Koreans but people worldwide. (PRISMA-P 2015).

Coll Antropol. (2005) stated that in terms of physiological characteristics, it has been found that elite taekwondo athletes tend to possess low levels of body fat moderate to high levels of cardio-respiratory fitness, and high levels of both aerobic and anaerobic physical fitness Sports Medicine (2014) while muscle strength is often not a key role (Rehabil 2015). In terms of specific physical fitness characteristics, successful taekwondo athletes were found to possess significantly higher maximum running speed better performance on 30m runs, countermovement jump, moving sideways, and walking backward. (PLoS One. 2019).

Additionally, research on the physical fitness test (PFT) of junior taekwondo athletes revealed that the power of lower extremities, strength, and endurance are of great importance to the result of the sport (Forrow 2018) However, the aforementioned studies are limited by the fact that the PFTs performed were all conducted during training because there is a big difference between training and competition modes for athletes' psychological and physical conditions Therefore, further study on the relationship between PFT and athletes' competition performance is still required.

A recent meta-analysis examining the effects of martial arts training on mental health examined 14 studies and found that martial arts

training had a positive effect on mental health outcomes. The study found that martial arts training had a medium effect size regarding reducing internalizing mental health problems, such as anxiety and depression; and a small effect size regarding increasing wellbeing (Moore et al., 2019).

Taekwondo training has positive effects on psychosocial factors such as sociality, character, etiquette, and school-life adjustment. Specifically, Taekwondo trainees exhibited significantly higher self-assessed scores on cooperation, law-abidance, leadership, responsibility, sociability, and stability among the subfactors of sociality. In the character subfactor, Taekwondo trainees were found to have a higher sense of community, consideration, emotionality, leadership, propriety, living, self-establishment, and self-esteem. In terms of etiquette, Taekwondo trainees had better qualities in terms of deportment, greeting, interpersonal etiquette, language, listening, phone etiquette, etiquette in public places, dining etiquette, and visiting etiquette. Finally, the improved psychosocial characteristics seem to be associated with better school-life adjustment, as evidenced by higher scores on learning, friendship, rule compliance, and teacher relations in Taekwondo training students relative to non-trainees (Lim, 2009).

According to Skelton (1991), one may benefit from the study of Taekwondo regardless of age, size, or athletic ability. Taekwondo training can increase strength and muscle tone, reduce body fat, improve cardiovascular conditioning and endurance, improve balance and coordination, reduce stress, improve concentration and focus, improve performance in one's job, school, or sports, and provide a structured program of advancement with achievable goals, and improve self-discipline and self-confidence.

According to Akande, Vanwyk, and Osagie (2000), exercise makes the human body stronger by increasing the blood flow to the brain. Evidence suggests that remaining physically fit will help people maintain their cognitive abilities as they age. In addition, exercise and good nutrition may enhance treatment for those with even the most severe mental disorders. There are also physiological benefits to be gained from regular exercise. Benefits are gained from regular activities like aerobic dance, cycling, walking stairs instead of using the elevator, and most importantly brisk walking. Any of these exercises done briskly will help ease stress and tension, and rejuvenate the body and spirit (Akande, Vanwyk, & Osagie, 2000)

Taekwondo training in the US was focused on health and physical-strength improvements in the past; however, approaches that address the value of education has recently become more popular. To prior studies, taekwondo training during the elementary school period has positive effects on physical, cognitive, emotional, and social development (Chang & Hwang, 2017; Lee & Song, 2006).

A key issue for practitioners working in competitive sports is enhancing the design of practice to facilitate the transfer of skills from training to competition. One way to enhance practice is by simulating key aspects of competition through the design of representative learning tasks or training (Araujo et al., 2007; Pinder et al., 2011b; Barris et al., 2014).

Taekwondo is a representative exercise that can help promote the physical, mental, and social development of young people, and is also widely supplied not only in Korea but also across the globe. According to Yim and Yang (2018), the trainees of Taekwondo aim to help themselves learn about the concept of self-realization, that is, the Way, and apply it to their lives by cultivating the mental world through physical training and practice.

In particular, unlike many general sports, Taekwondo does not place importance on the participation itself, but on the positive influence on the behavior and mind of the trainees via the training process. The effectiveness of Taekwondo is also intimately related to the training program. The training program has consisted of the basic movements of Taekwondo such as kicking, striking, throwing, and blocking, as well as Poomsae, which is practiced in a certain line of movements through the principle of hand and foot techniques against a virtual opponent, along with the main application of kicking embedded with sports like meaning, and Gyeorugi (or sparring), a movement of application, Shibeom, or demonstration to show the technique to the world outside, and the self-defense techniques for protecting one's self.

Recently, the Taekwondo Center training programs have been diversified and include various application programs including everyday etiquette education, character education, school physical education, recreation, promotion and promotion, examination events, participation in various contests, outdoor events, etc. While there are experts who are critical of the introduction of application programs that go beyond the essence of Taekwondo, the general view is that the provision of such programs will contribute to bringing about positive change for the trainees. That is, the aforesaid Taekwondo programs include basic movements, Taekwondo techniques including Poomsae and Gyeorugi, physical education for school physical education and various physical skills, plays including recreation and various events, and mental education including everyday etiquette and character education. However, such programs are structured differently for each Taekwondo center and according to the leader's competency (International Journal of Martial Arts, 2020).

The Taekwondo program adheres to multiple training principles, among which the leader provides various positive feedback while instructing the trainees not only to overcome the difficult training process but master Taekwondo techniques. Furthermore, it is the leader who plays a most instrumental role in the popularization and activation of Taekwondo, the cultivation of correct awareness, and the development of the instruction program. According to Huh (2020), 'the quality of education cannot surpass that of teachers.' This demonstrates how important teachers are in education, and what the teachers believe and how they behave can be said to be the criterion for determining the success or failure of education. It is undeniable that the Taekwondo program and its leaders have played an instrumental role in the development of Taekwondo. Taekwondo has become a foundation for dissemination not only in Korea but also across over 200 countries around the globe for the first time in 30 years, and this is because it has been designated as an important

symbol of Korean culture and the formation of the Taekwondo Park is promoted as a national project. (International Journal of Martial Arts, 2020).

In Alaminos City Division, different Taekwondo training program in both the private and public sectors were implemented. The assessment of these training programs is needed. Besides, Taekwondo has been well received by schools and parents who expected it would assist students in adapting to school life and in forming desirable etiquette and character during a critical period of development. Many of today's young students are forced to live a uniform and passive life within the framework set by adults and experience social disconnection due to a lack of family integrity, highly competitive education, and school violence, along with increased time spent on online activities (Hong, 2017).

Likewise, this is of great importance to hone the two elements – discipline and respect. These two pillars are the foundations on which students reach a new level of Taekwondo graduation and achieve a new belt color. Specifically, dedication and movement repetition are required to improve martial art movements. Through these activities, children develop self-discipline and self-restraint, traits and values that they instill in their own lives. Consequently, youth learn how to resist the urges to give in to peer pressure, and get involved in substance use and violence.

Research Questions

This study focused on the assessment of the Taekwondo training program in the division of Alaminos City for the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What is the status of the existing taekwondo training program along:
 - 1.1. basic movements (kibondongjak);
 - 1.2. forms (poomsae); and
 - 1.3. sparring (kyorugi)?
2. What is the effect of the implementation of the Taekwondo training program along:
 - 2.1. physical fitness;
 - 2.2. mental health; and
 - 2.3. emotional development?
3. What is the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the taekwondo training program along:
 - 3.1. pre-training;
 - 3.2. training proper; and
 - 3.3. post-training?
4. What are the challenges encountered in the implementation of the taekwondo training program?
5. What innovative Taekwondo training design was proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research. According to Trochim, (2015), descriptive research methods are those that seek to objectively measure the variables of interest. To qualify and quantify the effects of learner's perception on behavioral choices, this study offers a guide to the data collection and analysis, which provides useful information that is relevant to pre-service and practicing this research, a structured questionnaire was selected as a research tool.

Furthermore, Groves et al. (2015) explained the fact that questionnaires are utilized by researchers to convert information directly given by people into data. The findings suggest that classroom management has an impact on how learners learn and how educators manage to learn in a classroom situation.

According to Wasll (2015), descriptive research is a formal, objective, systematic process to describe and test relationships and examine cause and effect interactions among variables. Surveys were utilized for descriptive, explanatory, and exploratory research. Moreover, a survey is utilized to collect original data for describing a population too large to directly observe. A survey obtains information from a sample of people using self-report, that is, the people respond to a series of questions posed by the investigator (Frey, et, al 2014). In this study, the information was collected through self-administered questionnaires distributed digitally or personally to the respondents by the researcher. The research instrument was the use of a questionnaire to gather information from the respondents. Likewise, quantitative research techniques using the Likert scale were utilized.

Respondents

This study was conducted at Alaminos City division. There were ten (10) public and private secondary schools included in this study.

Table 1 presents the distribution of the population.

Respondents of the study were Taekwondo athletes with four years of experience in the field of taekwondo in all public and private secondary schools. The locale of the study was selected due to the reason that the researcher is a part of the SDO teaching personnel.

The total number of respondents was ninety-six (96) Taekwondo Athletes from SDO Alaminos City. The sample size of the population was determined using Yamane's formula and the stratified random sampling technique. The sample size was computed as $n = N / (1 + Ne2)$ at a .05 level of significance.

Table 1. *The population of the Study*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>No. of Taekwondo Athletes</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>
Alaminos City National High School	22	18
Alos National High School	15	12
Cayucay National High School	8	7
Colegio San Jose de Alaminos	12	10
Inerangan National High School	9	7
Pangapisan Integrated High School	11	9
Polo National High School	17	14
San Vicente National High School	18	15
Telbang National High School	2	2
The Great Plebeian College	2	2
Total	116	96

Instruments

In this study, the information was collected through self-administered questionnaires distributed personally to the respondents by the researcher. The research instrument is a questionnaire which intends to gather information from the respondents. Likewise, quantitative research techniques using the Likert scale were utilized. This study makes use of the descriptive research design.

Descriptive research, according to Wasst Kahn (2006), uses quantitative methods to describe what is, describe record, analyze, and interpret conditions that exist. It involves some type of comparison or contrast and attempts to discover relationships between existing non-manipulated variables. It is primarily concerned with the present, although it often considers past events and influences as they relate to current conditions. The extent of the conditioning activities and the level of satisfaction of the Taekwondo athletes was the two existing non-manipulated variables that need to compare to discover their relationships.

A survey questionnaire was utilized as the primary tool for gathering the needed data. The initial draft was prepared by the researcher and reviewed by the advisers. The survey questionnaire for the respondents consists of the following parts. The questionnaire was divided into three parts. Part I dealt with the status of the existing taekwondo training programs in terms of basic movements (kibondongjak), forms (poomsae), and sparring (kyorugi). Part II dealt with the effect of the implementation of the taekwondo training program along physical fitness, mental health, and emotional development. Part III dealt with the level of satisfaction with the implementation of the taekwondo training program in terms of pre-training, training proper, and post-training. Lastly, Part IV dealt with the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Taekwondo training program.

To obtain good reliability and validity of the survey questionnaire, the researcher sought the help of validators. The set of validators included the research adviser, a MAPEH head teacher, and a tournament manager or the person in charge of taekwondo in the SDO Alaminos City. Cronbach's alpha was utilized to measure the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire. The computed Cronbach alpha reliability of 0.94 shall imply that the instrument that was utilized in this study is 94% reliable. The reliability coefficient was calculated using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient formula. The correlation coefficient of 0.75 was considered adequate to judge the reliability of the instruments.

In addition to that, data collection started by applying for a research permit from the Schools Division Superintendent of Alaminos City. The researcher administered the questionnaires in cooperation with the school heads and discussed the guidelines on how to give the response to the questionnaires. Once the questionnaires have been given to the respondents the researcher retrieves them after a week, recorded and statistically treated.

Procedure

The implementation of the study was undertaken by the researcher after permission was secured from the authorities of Alaminos City division. Proper communication was coordinated to the School Heads before the distribution of questionnaire. The researcher oriented the respondent-athletes before the distribution of questionnaire. The conduct of the study sought the help of the school heads concern and other officials or teachers who are directly involved in the study.

Further, the researcher retrieved the same questionnaire and responses. The purpose and objectives of the study were clearly explained. Utmost confidentiality was assured to avoid inhibitions from the respondents in accomplishing the questionnaire. The respondents were asked to choose their preferred response by checking the appropriate box.

Data Analysis

The data that were gathered from the questionnaire were subjected to appropriate tools to answer the specific problems of the study. The data were tallied, organized, tabulated, and presented in textual and tabular form.

The weighted mean was used to determine the status of the taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division. The following scale/legend was used to interpret and analyze the data to be gathered.

Mean Scale Value	Point Value	Descriptive Rating
4.50 – 5.00	5	Very Satisfied
3.50 – 4.49	4	Moderately Satisfied
2.50 – 3.49	3	Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied
1.50 – 2.49	2	Moderately dissatisfied
1.00 – 1.49	1	Very dissatisfied

The weighted mean was used to determine the effectiveness of the implementation of the training program along physical fitness, mental health and emotional development. The following scale/legend was used to interpret and analyze the data to be gathered.

Mean Scale Value	Point Value	Descriptive Rating
4.50– 5.00	5	Very Effective
3.50 – 4.49	4	Effective
2.50– 3.49	3	Moderately Effective
1.50– 2.49	2	Slightly Effective
1.0 – 1.49	1	Not Effective

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program along pre-training, training proper and post training. The following scale/legend was used to interpret and analyze the data to be gathered.

Mean Scale Value	Point Value	Descriptive Rating
4.50 – 5.00	5	Very Highly Satisfied
3.50 – 4.49	4	Highly Satisfied
2.50 – 3.49	3	Moderately Satisfied
1.50 – 2.49	2	Slightly Satisfied
1.0 – 1.49	1	Not Satisfied

For the challenges encountered by the athletes', weighted mean was also used.

The data of the study were processed, organized, and summarized through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 26).

Results and Discussion

This section presented the data collected, statistical analyses made, and the interpretation of the salient findings. The result of the analyses of the data were organized in tabular form and sequenced in the order of the specific research problems that they are intended to answer.

Status of Existing Taekwondo Training Program

Tables 2, 3, and 4 show the status of existing taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along basic movements (kibondongjak), forms (poomsae, and sparring (kyorugi).

Status of Taekwondo Training Program Along Basic Movements (Kibondongjak)

Table 2 shows the status of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along basic movements (kibondongjak).

Table 2 shows that with regards to the taekwondo training program along basic movements (kibondongjak), the athletes are moderately satisfied to all of the training aspects particularly on the movements with “attacking from a distance,” which got the highest mean, 4.50. Likewise, the athletes are also moderately satisfied with their training on “from close and clinch,” 4.48 mean; and with “defensive kicks,” 4.46 mean. Further, they are moderately satisfied with their training on “stance and movement,” 4.44 mean; and “defensive hands,” 4.42 mean.

This result means that the athletes are not fully satisfied on the training program in Alaminos City division and that they look forward for improvement on the activities being implemented. This then implies that the people in-charge of the training program should assess and find ways to make the training program more innovative and engaging to the athletes.

The overall weighted mean, 4.46 shows that the taekwondo athletes are moderately satisfied with the overall training program of Alaminos City division particularly on basic movements or kibondongjak. This means that there must be some points to take note of and must be addressed to fully satisfy the trainings needs of the athletes. This result implies that the athletes assess the training program to be still lacking and that it needs further enhancement. Aligned with these results is the study of Ojeda-Aravena et al. (2021) that indicates significant effect of the time factor in both groups for squat-jump performance and a significant decrease for kick decrement index in repeated sprints, and in addition there is an improvement in performance according to the effect size analysis in the specific

techniques in total kicks, kick decrement index and 20m shuttle run. They even concluded that the addition to the regular training of a high intensity interval training with specific techniques and repeated sprints associated with intervals and similar structure of the combat during 4 weeks training can improve the concentric characteristics of lower limb performance, although they were not the sufficient stimuli in the other components of TKD-related fitness.

Table 2. *Status of Taekwondo Training Program Along Basic Movements (Kibondongjak)*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Stance and Movement	4.44	Moderately Satisfied
2. Attacking form Distance	4.50	Moderately Satisfied
3. From close and clinch	4.48	Moderately Satisfied
4. Defensive kicks	4.46	Moderately Satisfied
5. Defensive hands	4.42	Moderately Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean	4.46	Moderately Satisfied

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Satisfied; 3.51 – 4.50, Moderately Satisfied; 2.51 – 3.50, Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied; 1.51 – 2.50, Moderately Dissatisfied; 1.00 – 1.50, Very Dissatisfied

Status of Taekwondo Training Program Along Forms (Poomsae)

Table 3 shows the status of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along forms (poomsae).

Table 3 shows that with regards to the taekwondo training program along forms (poomsae), the athletes are highly satisfied on the training aspect referring to forms particularly on the “significance,” which got the highest mean, 4.74. However, the athletes are moderately satisfied to the other training aspects along forms such as on pattern, practical use, and self-style which all got a 4.49 mean. Likewise, they are moderately satisfied on their training referring to “stance” 4.47 mean. These results show that the athletes are very much particular to some aspects in their training referring to forms (poomsae) but at somehow fully satisfied with the “significance” in their taekwondo training. Although, this result implies that the sports officials or trainers must take into considerations the assessments made by the athletes as a baseline for further development of the training activities being implemented in the program.

The overall weighted mean, 4.54 shows that the taekwondo athletes are moderately satisfied with the overall training program of Alaminos City division particularly on forms or poomsae. This means that the trainers, coaches or sports managers should look into possible activities that could enhance the training program. This affirms Kim et al. (2021) study on the psychosocial effects of taekwondo trainings. The meta-analysis findings support that taekwondo can have a positive impact on the psychosocial factors of trainees.

Table 3. *Status of Taekwondo Training Program Along Forms (Poomsae)*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pattern	4.49	Moderately Satisfied
2. Significance	4.74	Very Satisfied
3. Practical Use	4.49	Moderately Satisfied
4. Self-style	4.49	Moderately Satisfied
5. Stance	4.47	Moderately Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean	4.54	Very Satisfied

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Satisfied; 3.51 – 4.50, Moderately Satisfied; 2.51 – 3.50, Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied; 1.51 – 2.50, Moderately Dissatisfied; 1.00 – 1.50, Very Dissatisfied

Status of Taekwondo Training Program Along Sparring (Kyorugi)

Table 4 shows the status of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along sparring (Kyorugi).

Table 4 shows that with regards to the taekwondo training program along sparring (kyorugi), the athletes are moderately satisfied on all the training aspect referring to sparring particularly such as “1st – Saebon Kyorugi (3-step sparring)” and “2nd – Dubon Kyorugi (2-step sparring),” which both got the highest mean, 4.50. Likewise, the athletes are moderately satisfied to the other training aspects along forms particularly on “3rd – Hanbon Kyorugi (1-step sparring) and “4th – Hanbon Macho Kyorugi,” which also both got a 4.26 mean. They are moderately satisfied too, on their training referring to “other sparring techniques” 4.20 mean. These results show that the athletes are critical to some aspects in their training on sparring (kyorugi) and that they are not fully satisfied. Hence, this result implies that those people in-charge of taekwondo program in the division or even the coaches should make further assessment of the training activities being implemented. This result goes with Seo & Park (2017), found that after 12 weeks of quality intervention, not only the physical condition of primary school students was improved, but also the dynamic and static balance was improved, and it was considered that the quality of Taekwondo was an effective sport.

The overall weighted mean, 4.34 shows that the taekwondo athletes are moderately satisfied with the overall training program of Alaminos City division particularly on sparring or kyorugi. This means that the athletes find the training program lacking and that the activities should meet their needs most especially when they have to join competitions. Further it implies that that the trainers, coaches or sports managers should look into possible activities that could enhance the training program. This result affirms the study of

Kamadulis et al. (2018) which used both specific training and sport-specific tests in pre- and post-testing. To improve performance in striking combats sports athletes, training should be specific to the sport demands.

Table 4. *Status of Taekwondo Training Program Along Sparring (Kyorugi)*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. 1st – Saebon Kyorugi (3-step sparring)	4.50	Moderately Satisfied
2. 2nd – Dubon Kyorugi (2-step sparring)	4.50	Moderately Satisfied
3. 3rd – Hanbon Kyorugi (1-step sparring)	4.26	Moderately Satisfied
4. 4th – Hanbon Macho Kyorugi	4.26	Moderately Satisfied
5. Other sparring techniques	4.20	Moderately Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean	4.34	Moderately Satisfied

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Satisfied; 3.51 – 4.50, Moderately Satisfied; 2.51 – 3.50, Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied; 1.51 – 2.50, Moderately Dissatisfied; 1.00 – 1.50, Very Dissatisfied

Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program

Tables 5, 6, and 7 show the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along physical fitness, mental health, and emotional development.

Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Physical Fitness

Table 5 shows the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along physical fitness of the athletes.

Table 5 shows that with regards to the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program along physical fitness, the athletes found it very effective with regards to the improvement of their balance and posture, and also on their aerobic fitness, assessing it with the highest mean, 4.64.

Likewise, the athletes found that the physical fitness implemented particularly on “coordination” to be very effective with 63 mean; and strength, 4.61 mean. They found “flexibility,” 4.52 mean to be least among the physical fitness indicators. This result means that the athletes find the effect of the implementation of the training program in Alaminos City division to be very effective on their end. This implies that the athletes felt that they have a good physical and are ready for the activities that may come anytime particularly taekwondo exhibition or competition.

The overall weighted mean, 4.60 shows that the taekwondo athletes found the effect of the implementation of the taekwondo training program to be very effective. Hence, the athletes must have felt their improvement in their physical conditioning. Thus, this implies that the taekwondo training program set of activities is working well for the overall improvement of the physical health condition of the athletes. These results are comparable to the study of Seok-Nam and Lim (2019) on their review and meta-analysis of different studies in which 14 studies applied taekwondo training for 12 weeks, 11 studies applied an exercise frequency of 5 sessions per week, 15 studies applied an exercise time of 60 minutes per session. The training contents included warm-up, physical training, basic movement, poomsae training, and self-defense, and cool-down. The frequency of the training used for physical training in the Korean taekwondo was higher in the order of power exercise, muscle endurance exercise, and cardiopulmonary endurance exercise.

Table 5. *Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Physical Fitness*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Improved balance/posture	4.64	Very Effective
2. Flexibility	4.52	Very Effective
3. Strength	4.61	Very Effective
4. Coordination	4.63	Very Effective
5. Aerobic Fitness	4.64	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	4.60	Very Effective

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Effective; 3.51 – 4.50, Effective; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately Effective; 1.51 – 2.50, Slightly Effective; 1.00 – 1.50, Not Effective

Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Mental Health

Table 6 shows the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along mental health of the athletes.

Table 6 shows that with regards to the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program along mental health, the athletes found it very effective with regards in exercising the mind, assessing it with the highest mean, 4.59.

Likewise, the athletes found that the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program with respect to mental health to be effective particularly on how they answer questions related to the use of their growing skills, and on the development of their awareness of what’s going on around them and how they relate to their environment, got 4.50 mean. The results of this study complement the study of Moore et al. (2019) with the meta-analysis examining the effects of martial arts training on mental health examined 14 studies

and found that martial arts training had a positive effect on mental health outcomes. The study found that martial arts training had a medium effect size regarding reducing internalizing mental health problems, such as anxiety and depression; and a small effect size regarding increasing wellbeing.

They found the training program effective among themselves in making them relax and free from stress, worries and/or anxiety, 4.40 mean. This result means that the athletes find the effect of the implementation of the training program in Alaminos City division to be effective in dealing with their mental health. This implies that the athletes received good activities in improving their mental health. However, they still find some points for improvement that could be helpful when they join taekwondo exhibition or competition. The overall weighted mean, 4.45 shows that the taekwondo athletes found the effect of the implementation of the taekwondo training program to be effective. Hence, the athletes must have felt that there are still factors to be considered to achieve the needed improvement in the training activities if they are to consider mental health. Thus, this implies that the taekwondo training program must be revised to meet the needs of the athletes to maximize the mental health conditioning of the athletes.

Table 6. Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Mental Health

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Exercise the mind	4.59	Very Effective
2. Memorize prearranged movements (forms)	4.27	Effective
3. Able to answer questions related to the use of their growing skills (use skills in the proper context)	4.50	Effective
4. Develop awareness of what's going on around them and how they relate to their environment	4.50	Effective
5. Relax and free from stress, worries and/or anxiety	4.40	Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	4.45	Effective

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Effective; 3.51 – 4.50, Effective; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately Effective; 1.51 – 2.50, Slightly Effective; 1.00 – 1.50, Not Effective

Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Emotional Development

Table 7 shows the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along emotional development of the athletes.

With regards to the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program along emotional development, the athletes found it effective with regards on the emphasis on positive social skills, assessing it with the highest mean, 4.50.

Likewise, the athletes found that the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program with respect to emotional development to be effective particularly on how they show strength and reliability in times of untoward circumstances or surprising situations, 4.38 mean; and on how they develop sense of responsibility and accountability for actions done regardless of the consequences, 4.30 mean.

Further, the athletes found the training program effective among themselves on how they develop the tools to manage and apply their energy in constructive ways-at home, school, and on the field; and on the intense release of nervous energy, 4.26 mean.

This result means that the athletes find the effect of the implementation of the training program in Alaminos City division to be effective in dealing with their emotional development. This implies that the athletes received good emotional activities in improving their self and emotions. However, they still find some grey areas that needs further development and improvement in the training program. Therefore, this implies that the sports management in charge of the training program must take account these results and formulate activities that could enhance the emotional development of the athletes. These results complement the study of Lakes et al. (2013) which reported that taekwondo training positively affected the self-control, execution functions, class behaviors, and exercise functions of young student subjects. The training also affected the school adaptation of the young students, as they experienced corresponding favorable effects regarding their relationships with teachers, their relationships with friends, and school classes and norms.

Table 7. Effect of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Emotional Development

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Intense release of nervous energy	4.26	Effective
2. Emphasis on positive social skills	4.50	Effective
3. Develop the tools to manage and apply their energy in constructive ways-at home, school, and on the field	4.26	Effective
4. Develop sense of responsibility and accountability for actions done regardless of the consequences	4.30	Effective
5. Shows strength and reliability in times of untoward circumstances or surprising situations	4.38	Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	4.34	Effective

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Effective; 3.51 – 4.50, Effective; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately Effective; 1.51 – 2.50, Slightly Effective; 1.00 – 1.50, Not Effective

The overall weighted mean, 4.34 shows that the taekwondo athletes found the effect of the implementation of the taekwondo training program with regards to emotional development to be effective. Most likely, the athletes have encountered these situations presented

and did not deal with them as they should have been dealt with. Hence, this implies that the taekwondo training program must be reviewed to check on areas where it needs priority improvement to enhance the emotional development of athletes.

Level of Satisfaction in the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program

Tables 8, 9 and 10 show the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along pre-training, training proper, and post training.

Level of Satisfaction in the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Pre-Training

Table 8 shows the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along pre-training.

With regards to the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program along pre-training, the athletes are very highly satisfied with “players were instructed that during sparring, there is no contact with the head allowed, and hard sparring is not permitted,” assessing it with the highest mean, 4.50.

Table 8. *Level of Satisfaction of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Pre-Training*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	The players were instructed that during sparring, there is no contact with the head allowed, and hard sparring is not permitted	4.75	Very Highly Satisfied
2.	The safety and precaution as a beginner are properly disseminated	4.63	Very Highly Satisfied
3.	Difficulties in motor skills were checked by the professionals	4.63	Very Highly Satisfied
4.	The training team ensures the provision of the mouth guard and padded cloth shin/instep guards	4.58	Very Highly Satisfied
5.	The training team provides warm-up and stretching exercises	4.52	Very Highly Satisfied
6.	The players were capacitated that sharing knowledge, and respect always come first	4.50	Highly Satisfied
7.	Inclusion of uniform consisting of a white t-shirt and black pants/leggings	4.49	Highly Satisfied
8.	Provision of orientation that the class is rooted in traditional values and techniques that we gear towards light-contact modern sparring	4.49	Highly Satisfied
9.	The physical abilities were properly examined before the training	4.45	Highly Satisfied
10.	The taekwondo players were instructed that class safety is a top priority and safety equipment is always utilized	4.32	Highly Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean		4.54	Very Highly Satisfied

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Highly Satisfied; 3.51 – 4.50, Highly satisfied; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately Satisfied; 1.51 – 2.50, Slightly Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.50, Not Satisfied

Likewise, the athletes have a very high level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo pre-training program with respect to the dissemination of safety and precaution for beginner, and on their difficulties in motor skills which were checked by the professionals, both at 4.63 mean.

However, the athletes have the least level of satisfaction on the implementation of the pre-training program on how the taekwondo players were instructed that class safety is a top priority and safety equipment is always utilized, 4.32 mean.

This result means that the athletes’ level of satisfaction varies depending on the situations met during the pre-training. Some of the athletes find the activities very highly satisfying and some find it to be just highly satisfied. This result shows that there is a gap on the satisfaction level which means that there are activities where the athletes are not completely satisfied. This implies that the athletes are expecting more in their pre-training activities and that the people in-charge should check on these areas where the athletes are not fully satisfied.

The overall weighted mean, 4.54 shows that the taekwondo athletes found the implementation of the taekwondo pre-training program to be very highly satisfying. Most likely, the athletes have experienced activities in the pre-training program that could meet their needs once they move forward to the next areas of the training program. This result affirms the study of Park & Seo (2017) which showed that 12-week Taekwondo can improve the posture stability and sports performance of primary school students, and it is also very effective in reducing the physical imbalance and improving the physical function of the growing children.

Level of Satisfaction in the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Training Proper

Table 9 shows the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along training proper.

With regards to the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program along training proper, the athletes are very highly satisfied with the “execution of high levels of lower limb muscular power which is in line with the demands of taekwondo combat under the current rules,” assessing it with the highest mean, 4.74.

Likewise, the athletes have a very high level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo pre-training program with respect to the development of their flexibility and strength, and on the provision of a hamstring exercise page with numerous ham string

strengthening exercises, 4.63 mean.

However, 7 out of the 10 indicators, the athletes found them only to be highly satisfying. The least among the indicators as per training proper of the taekwondo training program refers to “the performance of the lunge exercise helps your leg strength and flexibility,” which got only a 4.32 mean.

This result means that the athletes’ level of satisfaction did not meet the maximum, thus there are areas of the training that needs improvement. This implies that the athletes are considering their training proper to be reviewed and enhanced. As such, the sports managers, officials and anybody concern in the training program should sit together to polish the activities intended for the athletes. These results are similar to the study of Fong (2011), taekwondo training has a positive impact on physical health, such as improving physical fitness and body composition, and also on psychological, social, and cognitive health.

Table 9. Level of Satisfaction of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Training Proper

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Execution of high levels of lower limb muscular power which is in line with the demands of Taekwondo combat under the current rules	4.74	Very Highly Satisfied
2.	The flexibility and strength were developed	4.63	Very Highly Satisfied
3.	Provision of a hamstring exercise page with numerous ham string strengthening exercises	4.63	Very Highly Satisfied
4.	The provision of skills to maintain or repeat intense actions across combat	4.45	Highly Satisfied
5.	Plyometrics provides advanced training for explosive Taekwondo kicking power	4.32	Highly Satisfied
6.	The performance of a single-leg lift is safer than a double-leg left. Double leg lifts can put excessive strain on legs	4.32	Highly Satisfied
7.	The use of calf raises to strengthen calf muscles for Taekwondo	4.26	Highly Satisfied
8.	The execution of lateral jumps is also a great conditioning exercise	4.26	Highly Satisfied
9.	Execution of squat thrusts helps to build explosive leg power as well as work on other areas of your body	4.25	Highly Satisfied
10.	The performance of the lunge exercise helps your leg strength and flexibility	4.23	Highly Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean		4.41	Highly Satisfied

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Highly Satisfied; 3.51 – 4.50, Highly satisfied; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately Satisfied; 1.51 – 2.50, Slightly Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.50, Not Satisfied

The overall weighted mean, 4.41 shows that the taekwondo athletes found the implementation of the taekwondo training program to be highly satisfying. It seems that the result is good but actually it presents rooms for improvement.

Level of Satisfaction in the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Post Training

Table 10 shows the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division along post training.

Table 10. Level of Satisfaction of the Implementation of Taekwondo Training Program Along Post Training

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Through regular training, the athletes demonstrate high levels of cardio-respiratory fitness, excellent flexibility, outstanding dynamic upper and lower body strength, and good core endurance	4.75	Very Highly Satisfied
2.	The intense exercises gained from the training keep bodies healthy	4.74	Very Highly Satisfied
3.	Taekwondo helps students develop social skills	4.74	Very Highly Satisfied
4.	Taekwondo helps players thrive in tough times	4.74	Very Highly Satisfied
5.	The Taekwondo training developed the immune system	4.63	Very Highly Satisfied
6.	The spirit of camaraderie was also developed in Taekwondo training	4.63	Very Highly Satisfied
7.	The players generally feel more clear-headed and energetic after a hard workout, such as a taekwondo session	4.50	Highly Satisfied
8.	The five tenets of Taekwondo were developed courtesy, integrity, perseverance, self-control, and indomitable spirit	4.50	Highly Satisfied
9.	Build stamina and strength through punching and kicking drills, core-strengthening exercises, stretching, and fitness training.	4.36	Highly Satisfied
10.	The physical activity gained in taekwondo training is good for mental and emotional health	4.25	Highly Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean		4.58	Very Highly Satisfied

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very Highly Satisfied; 3.51 – 4.50, Highly satisfied; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately Satisfied; 1.51 – 2.50, Slightly Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.50, Not Satisfied

Table 10 shows that there is a high level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo post training program, the athletes assessed that through regular training, the athletes demonstrate high levels of cardio-respiratory fitness, excellent flexibility, outstanding dynamic upper and lower body strength, and good core endurance, the highest mean at 4.75.

Likewise, the athletes have a very high level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo post training program with respect to

the intense exercises gained from the training keep their bodies healthy, and taekwondo helps the students develop their social skills, 4.63 mean. These results mean that the athletes are very highly satisfied with the activities considering their physical health condition and social interaction. This means that the post training was able to develop them fully on these areas and that is manifested among the athletes.

The athletes have the least level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo post training program on the physical activity they have gained in training as per mental and emotional health are concern, which got only a 4.25 mean. This result means that the athletes' level of satisfaction did not fully reach their maximum expectation. This implies that the athletes have reservations on some of the activities and that the post training should be revisited and revised if found deemed necessary. These results are similar to the study of Zhang Peng (2018) which explored the impact of practical teaching on athletes' taekwondo quality and found that the shortage of equipment and lack of practical training are important factors affecting athletes' enthusiasm and Taekwondo quality. In this regard, we need to actively introduce Taekwondo equipment to meet the needs of athletes, and actively innovate the Taekwondo practice training mode, to further improve the level of students' Taekwondo.

The overall weighted mean, 4.58 shows that in totality the taekwondo athletes found the implementation of the taekwondo post training program to be very highly satisfying. Hence, this implies that the post training program can be retained at most but the indicators can be revisited individually to check on possible areas that need enhancement. Aligned with the study of Coyne et al., (2018), claimed that it is often thought that physical training is essential in Taekwondo sports. To effectively understand the full extent of the demands of a sport, researchers must not only examine the demands and implications of the competition itself but also the methods that coaches and athletes employ to prepare for competition. In open-skill sports such as taekwondo, where athletes are required to react to unpredictable and changing externally paced environments.

Challenges Encountered by Taekwondo Athletes in the Training Program

Table 11 shows the challenges encountered by the athletes while they are included in the taekwondo training program in Alaminos City division for SY 2022-2023.

Table 11 shows that the athletes encountered challenges particularly on “there is no budget intended to aid athletes with no enough money to buy their meals or snacks,” 4.76, the highest mean interpreted as very high. Likewise, the athletes encountered challenges, “The athletes should travel on their own from the school to the training venue” and “indefinite time of engagement with the coaches or trainers,” both at 4.70 mean described as very high. The lowest mean for the challenges encountered by the athletes, “training venue changes from time to time causing confusion among athletes,” 4.10 mean interpreted as high.

The overall weighted mean 4.45, shows that the athletes have highly encountered challenges in the taekwondo training program but were able to surpass by the athletes. This means that the athletes are growing together and are meeting the challenges of the training but somehow still need assistance from division and school officials. These results can consider the study of Liang (2019), taekwondo associations both in the public and private sectors are generally faced with the problem of insufficient professional quality of Taekwondo training programs and single curriculum content, which harms the improvement of Taekwondo athletes' actual ability, based on the development of Taekwondo courses. In this regard, it is necessary to actively improve the quality of training programs, innovate the types of Taekwondo courses, and stimulate athletes' interests in various forms such as competitive activities and competitions, to improve athletes' Taekwondo literacy.

Table 11. *Challenges Encountered by Athletes in the Taekwondo Training Program*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	There are no proper coordination between the coaches, trainers, and the school officials of the athletes, thus disallowing athletes to join practice	4.30	High
2.	There is no specific schedule for the athletes to follow to have their training or practice	4.25	High
3.	There are more opportunities being given to athletes with winning records	4.37	High
4.	There is no enough time for practice	4.55	Very High
5.	There is no specific place or area for continuous practice	4.20	High
6.	Training venue changes from time to time causing confusion among athletes	4.10	High
7.	Indefinite time of engagement with the coaches or trainers	4.70	Very High
8.	There is no financial support given by the local government, division or school to replenish supplies and equipment	4.60	Very High
9.	The athletes should travel on their own from the school to the training venue	4.70	Very High
10.	There is no budget intended to aid athletes with no enough money to buy their meals or snacks	4.76	Very High
	Overall Weighted Mean	4.45	High

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00, Very High; 3.51 – 4.50, High; 2.51 – 3.50, Moderately High; 1.51 – 2.50, Low; 1.00 – 1.50, Very Low

Conclusion

The following are the conclusions drawn from the salient findings of this study: In the status of taekwondo training program, the

athletes are moderately satisfied with their training on basic movements (kibondongjak), and sparring (kyorugi); and very satisfied with their training on form (poomsae).

In the effect of the implementation of taekwondo training program, the athletes found the training on physical fitness, mental health, and emotional development to be effective.

In the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program, the athletes are very highly satisfied with their pre-training and training proper; while they are very highly satisfied with their post training.

With the challenges encountered by the athletes in the taekwondo training program, the athletes have a high encounter.

On the challenges encountered, particularly on the issues on budget allocation and time allotment is very high.

The following are the recommendations forwarded based on the findings and conclusions of this study: In the status of taekwondo training program, there be a review and revision to be made to suit the training needs of the athletes particularly on basic movements (kibondongjak), and sparring (kyorugi) since they found it moderately satisfying.

In the implementation of taekwondo training program, the sports officials, coaches and trainers focus more on the training of athletes particularly on physical fitness, mental health, and emotional development.

In the level of satisfaction in the implementation of taekwondo training program, sports officials, coaches and trainers should strengthen the pre-training and proper training activities of the athletes.

On the challenges encountered by the athletes, the SDO personnel concern, coaches and trainers may always attend to the needs of the athletes to enhance their performance and be always on guard of their welfare.

With the challenges encountered on budget allocation or financial concerns of the training program and the athletes themselves, the training program be communicated to proper authorities for funding such as in the Special Education Fund or from potential stakeholders though private-public partnership program.

An innovative training design is being proposed, may this be used as a baseline data for the improvement of taekwondo training program in the division. The proposed innovative training design is attached as Appendix A in this study.

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